

Open Research for Net Zero

Transparency, openness, verification and reproducibility are important features of research that open research helps to uphold

Research in all disciplines increasingly relies on the use of DRI.

As well as being integral to a healthy research environment, open research and FAIR data practices can also promote more **efficient and collaborative use of the DRI.**

What is Open Research and FAIR data?

Open research relates to how research is performed based on the principle that research should be **as open as possible.**

This helps to improve public value, research integrity, reuse and innovation.

Open research also helps to support collaboration within and across disciplines.

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data stewardship provide guidelines to improve the **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, and **R**euse of digital assets.

FAIR data

FAIR data and code should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary. Embedding the FAIR principles within research practices is a key aspect of open research.

Findable

Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers.

Interoperable

Data should be available in a non-proprietary format where possible or information should be provided about how to use/where to get necessary software.

Accessible

Information required about how data can be accessed. Even if data is restricted, metadata should still be available.

Reusable

Information to promote reuse of data: metadata, licence describing any conditions and how data can be used, how, why and who created and processed the data

The benefits of open research for Net Zero DRI

Research in all disciplines increasingly relies on the use of DRI.

Open research and FAIR data practices can promote more efficient and collaborative use of the DRI.

- ❖ Developing Open Science and FAIR data standards, and providing training for researchers will maximise good practice, efficiency, data sharing, discoverability and reuse.
- ❖ Allowing others to reuse data and software promotes efficient use of the DRI by reducing unnecessary duplication of effort and compute
- ❖ This also reduces the need for extra data storage, making better use of embodied carbon in data storage systems.
- ❖ Collaboration in code writing for research can increase efficiency of DRI use through sharing of best practices in code design - learning from each other.
- ❖ Making research open and accessible extends the reach and impact of research outside academia

The challenges

Making research open whilst maintaining credit where credit is due

- ❖ Where research and data is made open, rightful credit must be given to authors. This should highlight the importance of robust open data policies and standards that ensure credit is correctly given to authors whilst data is made open.
- ❖ Embargos to give authors fair first-use and clear, correctly chosen licences supports researchers whilst allowing data to be opened for wider use.

The cost of FAIRification of data

- ❖ The process of making data FAIR requires an ecosystem of supporting tools and services that in turn require DRI resources. The balance in terms of net zero between effort put in and benefits derived is still unclear particularly when considering long term factors.
- ❖ We need to think critically about the data we store and its value to others for long-term preservation.
- ❖ This means making valuable datasets and software open and FAIR whilst not using resources to store data unnecessarily by clumping all output together.

There is a correlation between papers with open data having more citations than similar papers that don't.

A vision for UKRI DRI in 2040

“The UKRI DRI reputation for environmental excellence and its leading role in promoting productivity through Open Science policies and workflows attracts leading researchers from all over the world.”

